

From Research to Action: 18 months of research on the Video Games Industry Ecosystem & Strategic Recommendations for practitioners

Summary

GAMEHEARTS is an EU Horizon funded project examining the value of the European Video Game Industry Ecosystem (EVGIE) and its importance in contributing to economic growth, job creation, physical and mental wellbeing, and social and cultural cohesion. As part of the project's remit GAMEHEARTS partners at Wroclaw University of Economics and Business have identified mechanisms of value transfer and value co-creation by EVGIE and wider Creative and Cultural Industries. Their findings provide insight into the merits of cooperation and ascertains key recommendations to alleviate tensions in the process of inter-sector partnerships.

Research Design

As part of the **GAMEHEARTS project** (gamehearts.eu), an intensive and methodologically diverse research process was conducted to examine the functioning of the European ecosystem surrounding the video game industry. The course of this process is outlined below. Through the QR codes, you can access the full reports from specific research stages.

Literature analysis & case studies	Quantitative Survey	In-depth qualitative interviews	Focus group interviews	Design thinking-based marathons
<p>Data: 61 academic articles, 55 industry reports, and 18 statistical reports from the Statista database, 3 major & 6 minor cases</p> <p>Thematic scope: Co-creation of value, value transfer, co-innovation, 3E & 4E model of cooperation</p>	<p>Data: 1270 of European video game developers</p> <p>Thematic scope: level, scope, phases of co-creation & co-innovation relationships, innovativeness level, impact of co-innovation relationships on innovativeness of VGDs</p>	<p>Data: 27 interviews with representatives from EVGIE and CCI</p> <p>Thematic scope: impacts of VGI, cross-industry cooperation, strategic recommendations</p>	<p>Data: 1 national & 1 international focus group interview (8 game developers)</p> <p>Thematic scope: 5 insights from prior research steps investigated</p>	<p>Data: 3 national & 1 international edition (72 practitioners from EVGIE & CCI, 12 working teams)</p> <p>Thematic scope: cross-industry cooperation across 4E model, strategic recommendations</p>
<p>State of the Art Report</p>				

Recommendations for practitioners

Recommendations for practitioners, including VGD and representatives from other CCI	Beneficiaries	
	Direct	Indirect
<i>Cooperation</i>		
· Strategically cooperate at various levels, including intra-industry, cross-industry, intra-ecosystem, and/or inter-ecosystem.	VGD & CCI	Economy
· Take a proactive approach to cooperation and be more open-minded.	VGD & CCI	Economy
· Leverage mutual understanding, avoid tunnel vision and silo thinking (e.g. understand differences in business goals and organisational cultures).	VGD & CCI	Economy
· Communicate clearly and follow detailed reporting.	VGD & CCI	Economy
· Document and share both effective and ineffective practices.	VGD & CCI	Grant recipients
<i>Customers management</i>		
· Expand consumer perception in your strategy and product design.	VGD & CCI Customers	Economy
· Consider a broader approach to adopting the concept of user-driven innovations (e.g., not just gamers matter!).	VGD Customers	Economy
<i>Innovation management</i>		
· Increase innovativeness across different dimensions, including behavioural, product, and process innovativeness.	VGD	Customers Economy
<i>Products/Services portfolio</i>		
· Utilise inclusive and ensure that DEI rules are not implemented solely by force, and avoid diversity-washing practices.	VGD Customers	Society

Further Information

For more information please contact:

Professor Patrycja Klimas
patrycja.klimas@ue.wroc.pl

Project Website

Project LinkedIn

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